

PHENOXIDES OF TUNGSTEN

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Tungsten phenoxides of some mono-, di-, and tri-hydroxyphenols and mono- and di-nitrophenols have been prepared by the action of tungsten(VI) chloride on these phenols, their properties studied, and their constitutions discussed.

Funk and Baumann (*Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1937, **231**, 264) studied the action of WCl_6 on phenol and β -naphthol. They obtained $WCl_2(PhO)$ by digesting WCl_6 with $PhOH$ in the presence of CCl_4 on a water bath and $W(PhO)_6$ by the action of WCl_6 on $PhOH$. In a similar manner they obtained $WCl_2(C_{10}H_7O)_4$ and $W(C_{10}H_7O)_6$. Fernandes (*Gazzetta*, 1925, **55**, 424, 40) prepared the complexes of pyrocatechol and pyrogallol with MoO_2 , WO_3 , and UO_2 .

The present communication deals with a study of the phenoxides of tungsten by the action of some mono-, di-, and tri-hydroxyphenols and mono- and di-nitrophenols on tungsten(VI) chloride.

EXPERIMENTAL

The phenols and nitrophenols used were of B.D.H. or Merck's 'extra' pure quality. Ether (AnalaR) was distilled over metallic sodium.

Tungsten(VI) chloride was prepared by the action of chlorine on pure tungsten powder (Messrs. Johnson and Matthey) at 600° in a quartz tube in the complete absence of oxygen. Traces of tungsten(VI) oxychlorides were also formed but were sublimed off. Excess of chlorine was removed by passing well-dried, oxygen-free nitrogen. A solution of tungsten(VI) chloride, dissolved in anhydrous ether, was used in all the experiments.

General Method.—Ethereal solutions of WCl_6 and phenol or nitrophenol were mixed together; the mixture was slowly warmed at about $50-60^\circ$ in an oil bath for about half an hour. The temperature of the bath was then slowly raised and finally the residue was heated at a temperature of $10-12^\circ$ higher than the m.p. of the respective phenol. The heating was continued till the evolution of HCl had ceased. In all the cases the reaction was carried out in an atmosphere of nitrogen. The compounds obtained were washed with anhydrous ether and dried in vacuum. As the products obtained with resorcinol and orcinol were hygroscopic, these were quickly transferred to a vacuum desiccator and dried for 2-3 days.

A weighed quantity of the compound was digested with HNO_3 (conc.) for several hours on a water bath. It was then evaporated to dryness, ignited, and weighed as WO_3 .

Carbon and hydrogen were estimated in a few cases by combustion method and in the rest, the organic matter in the compound was found by difference. Nitrogen was estimated by Duma's method.

General Properties.—All the compounds are coloured, insoluble in CCl_4 , ether, and benzene but sparingly soluble in ethanol and acetone. The compounds formed with *o*-, *m*-, and *p*-cresols are, however, sparingly soluble in CCl_4 , ether, and benzene and soluble in ethanol and acetone. These are very stable in dry atmosphere, hydrolyse slowly on boiling with water, decompose when treated with acids or alkalies, and do not exhibit any coloration with ferric chloride.

TABLE I

Phenols.	Compound formed.	Colour.	% Tungsten.		% Org. matter.	
			Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
A. Tungsten(VI) chloride with monohydroxyphenols. WCl_6 : phenol = 1:6.						
α -Naphthol	$(C_{10}H_7O)_6W$	Black	17.37	17.65	82.63	82.35
					C: 69.46	69.10
					H: 4.25	4.03
o -Cresol	$(CH_3.C_6H_4O)_6W$	Greyish	22.59	22.27	77.41	77.73
m - "		black				
p - "		Black	22.24		77.76	
		"	22.40		77.60	
o -Nitrophenol	$(NO_2.C_6H_4O)_6W$	"	18.12	18.18	81.88	81.82
					C: 42.46	42.70
					H: 2.20	2.37
					N: 8.28	8.30
m - "		"	18.26		81.74	81.82
p - "	"	18.34		N: 8.29	8.30	
				N: 8.16	8.30	
2:4-Dinitrophenol.	$[(NO_2)_2.C_6H_3O]_6W$	Greyish brown	14.68	14.34	85.32	85.66
				N: 12.96	13.10	
2:4-Dinitro- α -naphthol	$[(NO_2)_2.C_{10}H_5O]_6W$	Shining black	11.86	11.63	88.14	88.37
				N: 10.74	10.62	
B. Tungsten(VI) chloride with dihydroxyphenols. WCl_6 : phenol = 1:3.						
Pyrocatechol	$(C_6H_4O_2)_3W$	Black	36.10	36.22	63.90	63.78
Resorcinol		Deep reddish	36.24	36.22	C: 42.68	42.53
Hydroquinone		brown			H: 2.24	2.36
Orcinol		Black	36.59	36.22	63.41	63.78
	$(CH_3.C_6H_3O_2)_3W$		33.68	33.45	66.32	66.55
C. Tungsten(VI) chloride with trihydroxyphenols. WCl_6 : phenol = 1:2.						
Pyrogallol	$(C_6H_3O_3)_2W$	Pitch-black	42.90	42.79	57.10	57.21
Phloroglucinol		Chocolate-brown	42.56	42.79	C: 33.68	33.49
				H: 1.46	1.40	
				57.44	57.21	

DISCUSSION

From the results it is evident that one molecule of tungsten(VI) chloride reacts with six molecules of a monohydroxy and three molecules of a dihydroxy and two molecules of a trihydroxy phenol. Nitro- and dinitro-phenols give similar results, only the hydroxy group being affected. The compounds formed can be represented as $W(C_{10}H_7O)_6$, $W(C_6H_4O_2)_3$, and $W(C_6H_3O_3)_2$ in the case of mono-, di-, and trihydroxy phenols respectively.

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